

Research on tribological characteristics of a new grease produced by mixed vegetable oil for low-speed application

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Abstract

This study explores the potential of vegetable oils as a sustainable alternative to mineral oils in grease formulation. The research focuses on producing bio-based greases using non-edible vegetable oils, specifically a blend of castor and jatropha oils in different proportions. Lithium hydroxide (LiOH) used as a thickener, while zinc dialkyldithiophosphate (ZDDP) additive was added to improve tribological properties of the bio- grease. According to factorial matrix, ten samples of bio-grease with different amount of base oil, thickener and additive were produced and tested for cone penetration, dropping point, wear, coefficient of friction, and viscosity using ASTM standards. Results showed that the bio-grease sample containing 3% thickener, 2% additive, and 10% jatropha oil (with the remaining 85% being castor oil) exhibited the best tribological characteristics among the samples. This sample achieved a wear value of 0.38mm and coefficient of friction value of 0.03511. The results indicate that a new produced bio-grease sample outperforms both the baseline research work and standard mineral EP3 greases. The blended oils' fatty acid composition contributed to improved film formation and lubrication, resulting in lower wear and friction coefficient values. This study concludes that blended non-edible vegetable oil with thickeners and additives can be used to formulate bio-grease, an environmentally friendly alternative to mineral-based lubricants.

Keywords: Bio-grease, base oil, lithium hydroxide thickener, zinc dialkyldithiophosphate additive

1. Introduction

Friction and wear are a cause of about 80% of mechanical failures, which also accounts for 25% of the world's energy consumption. To overcome this, researchers are concentrating on three main areas to lower friction: enhancing component design, developing advanced materials, and improving lubrication[1]. lubrication involves introducing a lubricant, such as oil or grease, between moving surfaces to facilitate the smooth movement of solid bodies by reducing friction between them. It protects against wear at contact surfaces, prevents corrosion, dissipates heat, controls contamination, and enhances overall efficiency. Effective lubrication plays a crucial role in conserving fuel and energy, making it essential for the optimal functioning of machinery and equipment [2].

Lubricants are divided into three categories based on their physical state: solid, semi-solid, and liquid. Grease, a semi-solid lubricant composed of 70–90 wt.% base oil, 5–20 wt.% thickening agent, and 0–5 wt.% additives, is often preferred for industrial and mechanical systems requiring reliable, long-lasting lubrication[3]. Base oils mainly used in grease production can be derived from mineral oil, synthetic oils, vegetable oils, or recycled used lubricant oils.

The global demand for lubricants is significantly increasing and thus the supply of petroleum is becoming increasingly limited. In 2022, the average global lubricant demand was 99.6 million barrels per day [4]. This

raise concerns about the finite nature of fossil fuel resources and their environmental impact. Widely used petroleum-based lubricants can pollute soil, lakes, rivers, and other natural habitats through leaks, spills, or improper disposal [5]. This situation emphasizes the need to find more sustainable alternative lubricants and due to these, the search for alternative lubricants has become a priority in recent years [6]. The alternative solutions include bio-based lubricants sourced from renewable materials, such as vegetable oils, animal fats, or synthetic esters, as well as lubricants formulated with advanced additives and base stocks that improve their environmental compatibility and other properties [2]. Bio-based lubricant offer a promising alternative lubricant to mineral oil lubricants due to their property includes low toxicity, better lubricity, lower emissions, higher flash point, lower volatility, higher viscosity index, and higher biodegradability over mineral oil [7][8].

2. Properties of vegetable oil

Vegetable oils are one of low toxic, higher viscosity and higher biodegradable bio-lubricant compared to mineral oils. These vegetable oils are suitable for both boundary and hydrodynamic lubrication because of the polar groups and long-chain fatty acids within their structure.[7][6][9]. While they offer numerous advantages over mineral oil, they also exhibit drawbacks such as low pour point and poor oxidation stability [8][7]. In general, as shown in table 1, vegetable oil-based bio-lubricants display a few amazing properties compared with mineral oils [10].

Table 1: Comparative evaluation of vegetable oils' characteristics [10].

Properties	Vegetable oils	Mineral oils
Density @200C (kg/m ³)	940	880
Viscosity index	100 to 200	100
Shear stability	Good	Good
Pour point, °C	-20 to 10	-15
Cold flow behaviour	Poor	-
Solubility in water	Not miscible	Not miscible
Oxidation stability	Moderate	Good
Sludge forming tendency	Poor	Good
Seal swelling tendency	Slight	Slight

2.1 Fatty acid profile of castor and jatropha oil

A completely saturated fatty acid has almost a straight carbon chain. When the hydrogen atoms are lost from the adjacent carbon molecules, the carbon atoms share a double bond rather than a single bond. This sort of fatty acid is known as an unsaturated fatty acid. In this case, the fatty acid is known as a polyunsaturated fatty acid if the double bonds happen in numerous locales [5]. Castor oil stands out among non-edible vegetable oils due to its hydroxylated fatty acids composition [11]. Castor oil has better viscosity at low temperatures and

better lubricating property at high temperatures compared to most vegetable oils [5]. The main fatty acid in castor oil is an unsaturated and hydroxylated fatty acid called ricinoleic acid (C₁₈H₃₄O₃) [12]. Different research indicated that the ricinoleic acid content of castor oil is approximately between 80% and 90% of its total fatty acid content, while the rest fatty acid content is approximately oleic 3.8-5%, Linoleic 2-4%, Linolenic 0.5-3%, Palmitic 0.5-1%, and Stearic% [12][6][1]. The hydroxyl group in ricinoleic acid gives to castor oil special qualities, such as high density, low iodine concentration, high viscosity, and high miscibility [12][13][1][5][14]. Jatropha oil has potential for lubricant production due to its high fatty acid content (61–64%). It has high unsaturated hydrocarbons (C₁₈:1) [5]. The polar heads of the fatty acids in jatropha oil react with the steel surfaces to form a protective soapy layer which helps to protect the surface against wear and has high oxidation stability [5] [15].

Table 2: Chemical compositions of vegetable oils [6]

Vegetable oil	Fatty acid							
	Myristic	Palmitic	Stearic	Palmitoleic	Oleic	Linoleic	Linolenic	Others
Jatropha	1.4	13-16	6-8	-	38-45	32-38	-	-
Castor	-	0.5-1	0.5-1		4-5	2-4	0.5-1	83-85 ¹
Cotton seed	1	22-26	2-5	1.4	15-20	49-58	-	-
Palm oil	1	37-41	3-6	0.4	40-45	8-10	-	-
Soybean	-	11-12	3	0.2	24	53-55	6-7	-
Sunflower	-	7	5	0.3	20-25	63-68	0.2	-

2.2 The effect of fatty acid content on vegetable oils property

The oxidation and lubricating characteristics of bio-grease are determined by the structure of the vegetable oil's fatty acids. Grease made from vegetable oil has poor thermo-oxidative stability as a result leading to weak wear protecting performance[16]. Excessive polyunsaturated fatty acids, such as linolenic acid, can contribute to undesirable oxidation and chemical instability when exposed to high temperatures [5], whereas some saturated fatty acids can negatively impact low-temperature flow properties. While research indicates that the presence of monounsaturated fatty acids within vegetable oil compositions improves their wear protecting performance, as well as thermal, and oxidative stability [1]. The shortcomings of vegetable oils can be addressed by blending of vegetable oils and modifying the vegetable oils chemically or incorporating suitable additives into the oils [17][18][9].

3. Materials and methods

3.1 materials and equipment

The raw materials and equipment used in this research are listed in table 3. Both ZDDP and LiOH were purchased from the local market, while the jatropa and castor oils were obtained by extracting from the jatropa and castor seeds that I found from the Amhara region, specifically from Bati local market. Blended jatropa and castor oil used as base oil for this experiment.

Table 3: List and description of raw materials and equipment

List of materials and equipment	Description
Blended castor and jatropa oil	Base oil (locally extracted)
Zinc Dialkyldithiophosphate	Anti-wear and antioxidant additives (found on local market)
Lithium Hydroxide	Thickener (found on local market)
Mixer	Used to mix the base oils, thickener and additive
Oven	Used for heating the mix
Thermometer	Used to measure the actual temperature
Digital balance	Used to measure the weight of the thickener
Viscometer	Used to measure the viscosity of base oil and grease
Tribometer	Used to test wear and friction
Penetrometer	Used to measure the grease penetration
Tachometer	Used to measure the rotational speed of the rotating motor
Digital vernier caliper	Used to measure the diameter of the specimen
Beaker (400 ml)	used to mix the base oil

3.2 Design of experiment

The experimental design (DOE) used a factorial approach (2^n) to determine the main variables affecting the characteristics and effectiveness of a bio-greases. This method examines the combined effects rather than varying factors individually by systematically altering the ratio of the factor across different experimental runs. The design of the experiment includes the independent variables, controlled variables, and dependent variables. [19].

A. Independent variable

In an experiment, independent variables are the factors those that are changed or modified to see how they affect the dependent variables, or response variables. In an experiment, independent variables are the factors those that are changed or modified to see how they affect the dependent variables, or response variables. It includes base oil (mixture of jatropa and castor), lithium hydroxide thickener, and zinc dialkyldithiophosphate additive. To analyse the effect of jatropa oil concentration on bio-grease performance, we selected minimum and maximum jatropa oil concentrations for input into statgraphics software, despite using a base oil mixture of jatropa and castor oil.

Table 4: Independent variable

No	Factorials	Min	Max	Units %
1	Jatropha oil ratio	10	20	%
2	Ratio of ZDDP	0.5	2	%
3	Ration of LiOH	2	3	%

B. Independent variable

The dependent variables are measurements or outcomes that are observed and recorded during an experiment to assess the impact of altering the independent variables. This response characteristics of the bio grease which are listed in the table 5 below are taken from previous studies and research that conducted the experiment using the ASTM standard. In particular, a bio-grease synthesized from unmodified castor oil and lithium soap thickener without any additive [20] and those made from blended jatropha and castor oil (1:1 ratio) with ZDDP additive and Sorbitan Monostearate Span 60 (SMS) thickener [21] show WSD values of 0.4mm and 0.6158mm respectively. Moreover, a grease produced from Lithium hydroxide monohydrate (LiOH.H₂O), stearic acid, soybean oil (SBO), and polysoap achieved a significantly lower COF of 0.015 [22]. From this two research, the Coefficient of friction test findings normally lie between 0.015 and 0.095, whereas wear values are between 0.04 and 0.6158mm. At the same time, for dropping point, viscosity, and cone penetration, their specific values are also based on ASTM standards.

Table 5: Dependent variables

Response	Min	Max	Units	Ref
Viscosity	0.5	18.02	Pa. s	[3]
Cone penetration test	220	250	dmm	[2]
Wear	0.4	0.6158	mm	[20] [21]
Friction coefficient	0.015	0.095		[22][21]
Dropping point	87.5	255<	°c	[23][24]

The factorial design (2^n), with three independent variables (n=3) and with two levels for each, typically requires $2^n = 2^3 = 8$ test runs. However, to enhance the reliability of the design and improve efficiency, the experimental matrix includes additional center points, resulting in a total of ten runs as selected by the experimental design software. The experimental matrix shown in tables 6 can be obtained in this way.

Table 6: Factorial experiment design matrix by using statgraphics

Run	Ratio of jatropa oil		Ratio of Castor oil		Ratio of thickener		Ratio of additive	
	%	g	%	g	%	g	%	g
1	20.0	30	77.5	116.25	2.0	3	0.5	0.75
2	15.0	22.5	81.25	121.875	2.5	3.75	1.25	1.875
3	20.0	30	76	114	2.0	3	2.0	3
4	10.0	15	86	129	2.0	3	2.0	3
5	20.0	30	75	112.5	3.0	4.5	2.0	3
6	10.0	15	86.5	129.75	3.0	4.5	0.5	0.75
7	20.0	30	76.5	114.75	3.0	4.5	0.5	0.75
8	10.0	15	85	127.5	3.0	4.5	2.0	3
9	15.0	22.5	81.25	121.875	2.5	3.75	1.25	1.875
10	10.0	15	87.5	131.25	2.0	3	0.5	0.75

Table 6 presents the experimental design matrix, generated using Stat graphics software, which shows the various possible combinations of independent variables for the experimental test runs. This design specifies the formulation parameters for ten distinct bio-grease samples. Based on this design of experiments (DOE) matrix, and assuming a sample weight of 150 grams, the total calculated amounts of castor oil and jatropa oil required for the entire experiment are approximately 1218.75g (1279ml) and 225g (246ml), respectively. An additional 30ml of base oil is added to each sample at the end of the reaction. Once produced, these samples will undergo tribological testing in accordance with ASTM standards to evaluate their performance characteristics.

3.3 Methods

The methods we follow in our research work: material preparation mentioned above in section 3.1, design of experiment which illustrated in section 3.2, sample preparation (mixing, saponification and homogenizing), sample characterizing and testing, and performance evaluation.

3.2.1 Sample preparation steps

The bio-grease formulation began with preparing all equipment, measuring apparatus, castor oil, jatropa oil, thickener (LiOH), and additive (ZDDP). Castor and jatropa oils were mixed in varying ratios per the experimental design, poured into a beaker, stirred, and heated at 60°C for 15 minutes. The thickener slowly added, followed by stirring and heating at 90°C for 60 minutes and then at 165°C for additional 30 minutes. After ninety minutes saponification, an additional 30ml base oil added while maintaining 180°C for 30

minutes. The additive incorporated, and heating continued at 90°C for 30 minutes. Finally, the mixture was stirred until cooling to room temperature for homogenization.

3.2.2 Sample bio grease property analysis

To evaluate the suitability and characterize the performance of each bio-grease sample, we conducted a series of laboratory tests. These tests included dropping point test, worked and unworked cone penetration test, viscosity measurement, wear, and coefficient of friction evaluation.

3.2.2.1 Wear and coefficient of friction

The tribological performance of the produced greases was evaluated using a simplified Timken load tester, following the ASTM D2509 standard test method [25]. This block-on-ring apparatus measures the coefficient of friction, wear (in terms of diameter loss) and, load-carrying capacity of lubricating greases. The test apparatus includes a lever arm to which weights are attached, a power meter that measures power consumption, a three-phase motor, and a shaft-and-ring assembly. The test sample is secured in a holder with a bolt and aligned perpendicularly to the ring, which is submerged in a container filled with the sample bio-grease. The sample block is made of brass, a material widely used in applications such as bearings, gears, valves, and base plates. The ring is made of cast iron, selected for its resistance to deformation and wear. According to the ASTM D2509 standard, 133.4 N force is applied at the lever, and the test is conducted for a duration of 10 minutes. The power consumption of the apparatus under the applied load is recorded using a power meter for each bio-grease sample throughout the test duration. If no scoring is observed on the block, the procedure is repeated for another 10 minutes with an additional applied force of 44.5 N.

Table 7: ASTM D2509 standard parameters for load carrying test

Parameter	ASTM D2509 standard
Rotating speed of the motor	800rpm
Duration	10min ±5sec
Load at lever	133.4 N
Temperature	24°C±6°C

Wear scar diameter of each bio-grease sample can be calculate using equestrian (3.1)

$$WSD = D_{bef} - D_{aft} \text{-----(3.1)}$$

Where, D_{bef} is diameter of specimen before test and D_{aft} diameter of specimen after test

The coefficient of friction can be calculate using equation (3.4)

$$\Delta P = W t = F \times d/t = F \times v \text{-----(3.2)}$$

$$\Delta P = P_{load} - P_{without load} = F_f \times V, \text{ where } F_f = \mu F_N \text{-----(3.3)}$$

$$P_{load} - P_{without load} = \mu F_N$$

$$\mu = (P_{load} - P_{without load}) / (V_{linear} \times F_N) \text{-----(3.4)}$$

Where, ΔP = the change of power before the load applied and after the load applied on the tribometer

P_{load} = the motor power consumption when operating under a certain load

$P_{without\ load}$ = The motor power consumption when operating without load

F_N = normal force applied on the ring

V_{linear} = Linear speed of the ring

$$V_{linear} = \omega r \text{-----} (3.5)$$

$$\omega = 2\pi N / 60 \text{-----} (3.6)$$

where, ω angular speed, r = radius of the ring and, N = rpm of the shaft (Speed of motor)

3.2.2.2 Dropping point temperature

The dropping point of grease represents the maximum temperature at which grease is suitable for use before it began to lose its structure. At temperatures beyond the dropping point, the grease loses its consistency and stiffness, while minor changes in consistency may occur with temperature fluctuations below the dropping point. Therefore, it is critical that grease maintain its consistency and stiffness within the expected range of operating temperatures [26]. The dropping point of grease can be measured by using ASTM D-2265 test standards. In this test method, the sample grease is placed in a test cup, which is then positioned inside a test tube. The test tube is immersed in a glycerol bath that is heated in an oven. As the temperature rises, the grease gradually melts, and at a specific temperature, a drop of melted grease will fall from the test cup to the bottom of the test tube. This temperature is recorded using a thermometer placed inside the test tube. After recording the value, the equipment is cleaned, and the procedure is repeated for each bio-grease sample.

3.2.2.2 Cone penetration

The consistency of grease refers to the resistance of the grease to deformation when force applied on it. It depends on or affected by the base oil viscosity and the concentration and type of thickener used [27]. The consistency values obtained are used to classify grease, ranging from 475 dmm for very soft grease to 85 dmm for very hard grease. Both worked and unworked greases penetration measured using ASTM D-217 standard test method [28]. This involves measuring the depth of penetration of a standardized cone assembly (brass cone a 45°-angled, 102.5-g weight) into the grease sample. For unworked penetration test, in which used to determine the unworked penetration value (UWPV), the sample is placed in a container or cup and brought to the penetrometer. The cone assembly is then released freely to the sample grease for a duration of 5 seconds and read the penetration result and recorded the value. For worked penetration, the grease first subjected to 60 double strokes in a grease worker before the same cone penetration test is carried out. In both cases, three readings are recorded and averaged taken for each sample to ensure accuracy [20].

3.2.2.2 Viscosity (ASTM D445)

The viscosity of the sample greases was measured by using ASTM D445) or (DIN 51562) standards [29]. The bio-grease dynamic viscosity was measured by using a rotational viscometer located at Addis Ababa Institute of Technology University's chemical laboratory.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1 Physical appearance of produced sample bio-grease

The bio-grease samples were produced using different proportion of jatropha and castor oil, ZDDP additive, and LiOH thickener. Due to these different proportions, each bio-grease demonstrated unique characteristics. The grease's performance and appearance were significantly influenced by these ratios. Increasing thickener ratio produced harder, more solid grease, whereas lower thickener content had the opposite effect. Following experimental design standards, thickener concentrations of 2-3% and additive concentrations of 0.5-2% were used. Grease samples with over 3% thickener were too solid to be usable, while those with under 2% were too fluid. Visual appearance of the produced grease samples influenced by the color of the base oils and the additive. Since the castor and jatropha oil were extracted using a mechanical oil extractor a pure oil was used without any bleaching. A purely extracted castor oil has a higher viscosity and has nearly light-yellow color, while jatropha oil has a dark brown color. As a result, a produced bio-grease samples have a brown and dark brown color.

Fig. 1: Produced sample bio-grease

4.2 Characteristics of produced bio-greases

4.2.1 Wear and coefficient of friction

Friction and wear characteristics of bio-greases produced from blended castor and jatropha oil were evaluated using a block-on-ring tribometer with a brass-on-cast-iron contact with an applied load of 133.4N at the lever. The following table 8 shows the result, detailing the performance characteristics (wear) of the tested bio-grease samples.

Table 8: Wear test results of the produced bio-grease

Sample	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	*11
D_{bef} (mm)	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14
D_{aft} (mm)	13.22	13.42	13.35	13.38	13.56	13.44	13.4	13.59	13.43	13.24	13.53
Applied load (Kg)	13.6	13.6	13.6	13.6	13.6	13.6	13.6	13.62	13.6	13.6	13.6
WSD (mm)	0.78	0.58	0.65	0.62	0.44	0.56	0.60	0.38	0.57	0.76	0.47
P_{load} (W)	560	401	453	443	367	395	427	349	407	556	384

*11 is Mineral EP3 grease

4.2.1.1 Analysis of wear result using Pareto chart

The standardized Pareto Chart displays a bar for each effect, arranged from most significant to least significant. The length of each bar is proportional to the standardized effect. Factors that cross the vertical line are statistically significant. As illustrated in figure 2, the chart for wear shows that the concentration of thickener (B) and additive (C) are the most significant factors affecting wear. The ratio of jatropha oil (A) and the squared effect of ratio of jatropha oil (AA), have a moderate effect on wear. In contrast, the interaction between ratio of thickener and additive (BC), the interaction between ratio of jatropha oil and thickener (AB), and the interaction between ratio of base oil and additive (AC) have negligible influence on wear. This suggests that to minimize wear, optimizing the ratios of thickener and additive is crucial, while the interactions between these factors are less critical.

Fig.2: Standardized Pareto chart for Wear

4.2.1.2 Analysis of wear result using main effects plot

The Main Effects Plot for Wear reveals the relationship between the wear level and the independent variables or factors. The plot in figure 3 shows that the ratio of thickener and additive have the most significant impact on wear, as concentration of thickener and additive increase wear value decrease. Furthermore, the ratio of jatropha oil has a minimal positive impact on wear. Wear initially decreases with increasing jatropha oil ratio, reaching a minimum at the midpoint value of the jatropha oil ratio, and then increases linearly as the jatropha oil ratio increases. On the other hand, increasing concentration of castor oil (decreasing concentration of jatropha oil) notably decreases wear. These results emphasize the importance of optimizing the ratio of thickener, additive, and castor oil, while keeping the ratio of jatropha oil at minimum to reduce wear.

Fig 3: Main effects plot for wear

4.2.1.2 Optimize response

According to the optimization table 9 which generated by the software, minimizing wear can be achieved by using higher levels of thickener and additive ratio. Specifically, the optimal combination includes ratio of jatropha oil at its optimum level (11.97%), ratio of thickener at its optimum level (2.99%), and ratio of additive at its maximum level (2.0%), with the remaining 85% consisting of castor oil.

Goal: minimize Wear, **Optimum value** = 0.377mm

Table 9: Optimized response for wear

No	Factor	Low (%)	High (%)	Optimum (%)
1	Ratio of jatropha oil	10	20	11.97
2	Ratio of thickener	2	3.0	2.99
3	Ratio of additive	0.5	2.0	2.0

4.2.2 Coefficient of friction

Excessive friction is one of a cause of mechanical failures and a major contributor to world's energy consumption. High coefficients of friction (COF) result in excessive friction forces and substantial energy losses. As a result, reducing COF is crucial for energy conservation and enhancing efficiency of mechanical system [1]. The coefficient of friction is can be calculated using equation (3.4) [30].

Table 10: Specified parameters of the tribological test machine

F_N	$P_{without\ load}$	ω	r	V_{Linear}
2199.89N	220W	83.77rad/s	200mm (0.02m)	1.67m/s

The coefficient of friction (COF) is calculated using Eqn.3.4, which considers the normal force on the ring, the ring's linear speed, and the motor's power consumption. As shown in Eqn.3.4, COF is directly proportional to power consumption; increased power consumption corresponds to a higher COF, and vice versa.

Table 11: coefficient of friction test results of produced bio-grease sample

Sample	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	*11
COF	0.093	0.049	0.063	0.061	0.04	0.048	0.056	0.035	0.051	0.092	0.045

4.2.2.1 Analysis of COF result using pareto chart

The following Pareto chart reveals that the most influential factors affecting the coefficient of friction (COF) which are the ratio of thickener (B), the ratio of additive (C), the squared effect of the ratio of jatropa oil (AA), and the interaction in the ratio of thickener and additive (BC). As shown in figure 4, the thickener and the additive ratio have a strong negative effect on COF, while the squared effect of the ratio of jatropa oil (AA) and the interaction between the ratio of thickener and additive (BC) exhibits a small positive effect on COF. Moreover, the ratio of jatropa oil (A), the interaction between the ratio of jatropa oil and thickener (AB), and the interaction between the jatropa oil ratio and additive (AC) have no influence on the COF within the experimental range.

Fig 4: Standardized Pareto Chart for COF

4.2.2.2 Analysis of COF result using main effects plot

The COF Main Effects Plot shows the effect of each independent variable on COF, with other independent variable held constant. The thickener and additive ratio have a negative effect on COF. However, the ratio of jatropha oil has a non-linear relationship, with COF first decreasing and then increasing as ratio of jatropha oil increasing. This indicates that COF influenced by a complex interaction between the jatropha oil and other variable. In general, increasing the ratios of thickener and additive leads to decrease in the coefficient of friction (COF). Sample 8 bio-grease, which had higher levels of thickener, additive, and low level of jatropha oil exhibited the lowest COF value.

Fig 5: Main effects plot for COF

4.2.2.3 Optimize response

Analysis of the Main Effects Plot and optimization results suggests that a combination of higher thickener (3.0%) and additive ratios (2.0%), along with a specific jatropha oil ratio of 14.3142 (with castor oil accounts for the remaining 80.68%), is predicted to minimize the friction coefficient. Table 12 indicates that this optimized combination is expected to yield a friction coefficient of 0.0265.

Goal: minimize COF, **Optimum value** = 0.0265

Table 12: Optimized result for COF

Factor	Low	High	Optimum
Ratio of jatropha oil	10	20	14.3142
Ratio of thickener	2	3.0	3.0
Ratio of additive	0.5	2.0	2.0

4.2.3 Viscosity

The dynamic viscosity of each produced bio-grease sample was measured at 40°C, with results indicated in table 13. The data indicates that samples 8, 5, 6, and 7 exhibited a higher viscosity characteristic compared to the other samples. However, mineral EP3 grease showed the highest viscosity than those samples.

Table 13: Viscosity test results of produced greases samples

Sample	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	*11
Viscosity at 40 °C in pa.s	4.98	10.29	5.72	8.07	12.3	13.63	11.7	14.57	10.34	6.84	15

4.2.3.1 Analysis of viscosity result using pareto chart

Standard Pareto Chart for Viscosity highlights that the thickener ratio (B) represented by the gray bar has the most significant influence on viscosity. As shown in the following figure 6, the jatropha oil ratio (A) also has a moderate effect on viscosity. However, the ratio of additive (C) and the squared effects of jatropha oil (AA) which represented by the blue bar have minimal effect on viscosity, while interactions between jatropha oil and additive (AC), the interaction between thickener and additive (BC), and the interaction between jatropha oil and thickener (AB) have negligible impacts on viscosity. This suggests that optimizing viscosity primarily involves adjusting the ratios of thickener, additive, and base oil (ratio castor and jatropha oil), while the influence of squared effect of jatropha oil (AA) and the interaction between these factors are less critical.

Fig.6: Standardized pareto chart for viscosity

4.2.3.2 Analysis of viscosity using main effects plot

The main effects plot for viscosity illustrated in figure 7, demonstrates a clear positive relationship between the viscosity and thickener ratio. This means that the viscosity (fluid's resistance to flow) of the bio-grease increases as thickener ratio increases from minimum to maximum level. The value of the viscosity is the highest at the maximum level of additive ratio, meaning with increasing additive ratio result relatively higher viscosity. In contrast, with increasing the amount of jatropha oil (decreasing concentration of castor oil) leads to decrease the viscosity of the bio-grease. This result suggests that a higher viscosity achieved by using maximum level of thickener and additive, combined with a minimum level of jatropha oil and higher amount of castor oil. Bio-grease sample 8 and 6 result a highest viscosity of 14.57 and 13.63 respectively during the experiment.

Fig.7: Main effects plot for viscosity

4.2.3.3 Optimize response

Higher viscosity of lubricant ensures effective film formation between contacting surfaces at high temperatures and used to reduce friction and wear. The optimum viscosity value of 14.589 in this experiment achieved with a combination of jatropha oil ratio at its low level (10.1), thickener ratio at its high level (3.0), and additive ratio at its high level (2.0) with castor oil accounts for the remaining 84.9%.

Goal: maximize Viscosity, **Optimum value** = 14.589 pa. s

Table 14: Optimized result for viscosity

NO	Factor	Low	High	Optimum
1	Ratio of jatropha oil	10	20	10.1
2	Ratio of thickener	2	3.0	3.0
3	Ratio of additive	0.5	2.0	2.0

4.2.4 Cone penetration

The unworked and worked cone penetration tests were performed on the bio-grease samples. Samples 8, 5, 6, and 7 exhibited lower penetration, but samples 1 and 10 showed higher penetration compared to the other samples. The cone penetration (worked) value of samples 8, 5, 6, and 7 are in the ranges of suggested minimum and maximum response level (NLGI 3).

Table 15: Grease sample cone penetration test

Cone penetration measurement in dmm										
Sample	unworked penetration					worked penetration				
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	Average	NLGI	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	Average	NLGI
1	346	339	334	339.66	1	363	368	364	365	0
2	295	291	287	291	2	318	329	325	324	1
3	334	327	329	330	1	355	359.5	358	357.5	0
4	316	310	307	311	1	325	331	334	330	1
5	229	222	224	225	3	247	242	249	246	3
6	224	221	218	221	3	235	243	241	240	3
7	230	228	226	228	3	253	246	258	249	3
8	200	204	202	202	4	226	223	217	222	3
9	290	288	292	290	2	322	331	325	326	1
10	331	336	329	332	1	359	355	363	359	0
*11	203	197	210	203	4	221	234	232	229	3

*11, Mineral EP3 grease

4.2.4.1 Analysis of cone penetration result using pareto chart

As shown in standardized Pareto chart below, the thickener ratio (B) represented by the blue bar has the most significant influence on the cone penetration. The squared effect of the jatropha oil ratio also has noticeable impact on the response next to thickener ratio. From Figure 8, it is clear that the additive ratio (C) and the jatropha oil ratio (A) have a moderate effect on the response, while interactions between jatropha oil and additive ratio (AC) has minimal influence on cone penetration. Finally, the interaction between thickener and additive ratio (BC) and the interaction between jatropha oil and thickener ratio (AB) have negligible effect on cone penetration.

Fig.8: Standardized Pareto chart for cone penetration

4.2.4.2 Analysis of cone penetration result using main effects plot

The Main Effects Plot illustrates how each factor influences the cone penetration of the bio-grease. The thickener ratio has a negative correlation with penetration depth, with a significant decrease in penetration depth as the thickener ratio increases. This is because a higher concentration of thickener generally increases the grease's stiffness and resistance to penetration.

Fig.9: Main effects plot for cone penetration

The penetration moderately decreases with increasing the additive ratio, indicating a minor stiffening effect. As shown in figure 9, the ratio of jatropha oil exhibits a non-linear relationship, with penetration depth initially

increasing and then decreasing with increasing jatropha oil ratio. Bio-grease sample 8 and 6 achieved best cone penetration result of 222dmm and 240dmm respectively during the experiment.

4.2.4.3 Optimize response

Table 16 illustrates the optimized combination of jatropha oil, thickener, and additive ratio within the experimental range, specifically designed to produce a grease with NLGI grade 3 consistency (220-250 penetration value), which is suitable lubricant in low-speed high load and continuous application (rolling and sliding bearings) [2]. As indicated in table 16 below the statgraphics software identified a minimum jatropha oil (maximum castor oil), maximum thickener, and maximum additive ratio as the optimal levels for maintaining penetration within the target range. Therefore, this experiment identified the optimal combination of factors to achieve the required cone penetration value. **Optimum value** = 221.188.

Table 16: Optimized result for cone penetration

Factor	Low	High	Optimum
Ratio of jatropha oil	10	20	10
Ratio of thickener	2	3.0	3.0
Ratio of additive	0.5	2.0	2.0

4.2.5 Dropping point temperature

The test result of dropping point temperatures for each bio-grease sample presented in table 17 below. Bio-grease samples 8 (141°C) and 6 (139°C) performed best result, indicating that stiff grease samples have high dropping point. Higher dropping points bio-grease have better thermal stability and useful for high-temperature applications [7].

Table 17: Dropping point test result for produced grease sample

Sample	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	*11
Dropping point in °C	94.5	114	101	110	127	139	122	145	113	97	178

4.2.5 Analysis of the dropping point temperature result using pareto chart

According to the pareto chart for dropping point, thickener ratio (B) is identified as the most influential variable affecting the dropping point of the bio-grease. The jatropha oil (A) also exhibited a notable effect on the response, while the ratio of additive (C) and the interaction between jatropha oil and thickener (AB) have comparatively smaller effect within the tested range.

Fig.10: Standardized pareto chart for dropping point temperature

However, the interaction between factors (BC, AC) and, squared effect of jatropa oil ratio (AA) showed negligible influence on the dropping point of bio-grease. This suggests that optimizing the thickener, jatropa oil ratio, and castor oil ratio is crucial for maximizing the dropping point of the grease.

4.2.5 Analysis of dropping point temperature result using main effects plot

The Main Effects Plot illustrated in figure 11 below further demonstrates the effect of each factor on dropping point temperature of the bio-grease. The thickener ratio has a positive slope, meaning that increasing thickener ratio resulted a significant increase in dropping point due to improved stability of the bio-grease at high temperatures. From the plot it is clear that increasing the jatropa oil ratio (decreasing the concentration of castor oil) slightly decreases the dropping point, likely because a higher amount of jatropa oil without a corresponding increase in thickener can compromise structural stability. Additionally, the additive ratio shows a minor positive effect on the dropping point within the tested range, with increasing additive ratio resulted slightly increase in dropping point temperature. The result suggests that optimizing the thickener, additive ratio, and castor oil ratio while minimize jatropa oil ratio are important for maximizing the dropping point of the grease.

Fig.11: Main effects plot for dropping point

4.2.5 Optimize response

This optimization identified the optimal combination of variable levels that maximizes the dropping point temperature. The suitable values of each independent variable are selected by the software. This analytical approach gives an optimum of combination of factors within the specified experimental range. The following table 18 shows possible combination of factors for achieving the highest possible dropping point temperature. Specifically, this optimal combination was achieved in Sample 8 which exhibited a dropping point temperature of 145°C during the experiment, demonstrating that the experiment successfully identified the factor levels necessary to attain the highest dropping point temperature.

Goal: Maximize dropping point temperature, **Optimum Value** = 145.688

Table18: Optimized result for dropping point

Factor	Low		High	Optimum
Ratio of jatropha oil	10		20	10
Ratio of thickener	2		3.0	3.0
Ratio of additive	0.5		2.0	2.0

4.3 Comparison of our result with baseline and mineral EP3 grease

4.3.1 Evaluation of wear and coefficient of friction

Figure 12 shows the comparison of our work sample 8 grease formulation to both standard mineral EP3 grease and baseline [21]. The result indicates sample 8 demonstrated superior performance with the lowest 0.38 mm wear scar diameter and 0.035 coefficient of friction. Bio-grease sample 8 consists of 85% castor oil, 10% jatropha oil, 3% LiOH thickener, and 2% ZDDP additive. Whereas baseline [21] grease formulation utilized 36% jatropha, 36% castor, 25% SMS thickener and 3% ZDDP additive. Due to the concentration enhancement and incorporation of LiOH thickener, sample 8 bio-grease achieved the best tribological performance compared to standard mineral EP3 grease and Baseline [21].

Fig.12: Comparison of sample 8 with mineral EP3 grease and baseline

4.3.2 Evaluation of cone penetration

Our research work focused on producing bio-grease for low-speed applications. The low-speed range applications required NLGI grade 3 with numerical scale of worked penetration range in between 220 and 250. Figure 13 shows the comparison of cone penetration values of our work samples 5, 6, 7, 8, with standard mineral EP3 grease test result

Fig.13: CPT comparison of selected samples with mineral EP3 grease

From table 15 above, we can clearly see that samples 5, 6, 7, 8, and mineral EP3 grease fall within the NLGI grade 3 classification. However, sample 5, 6, and 7 exhibit a relatively softer texture compared to sample 8 and the mineral-based EP3 grease. Notably, sample 8 demonstrates significantly higher stiffness than the other samples. These bio-grease samples used for low speed with high to moderate load application specifically sample 8 suited for low-speed, high-load application.

4.3.3 Evaluation of dropping point temperature

The dropping point of all produced bio-grease samples were compared with that of the standard mineral EP3 grease. Sample 1 and 10 achieved lowest dropping point temperature, making them unsuitable for higher temperature application. On the other hand, sample 2, 3, 4, and 9 achieved a moderate dropping point. These sample bio-grease have moderate thermal stability. As shown in figure 14, sample 5, 6, 7, and 8 exhibited higher dropping point temperature relative to the other samples, although still lower than the mineral EP3 grease. The mineral EP3 grease achieved the highest dropping point, showing superior thermal resistance. A high dropping point helps to minimize leakage from bearings at elevated temperatures.

Fig.14: Comparison of produced bio-grease samples with mineral EP3 on DPT

4.3.4 Evaluation of viscosity

Figure 15 below, shows the comparison of the viscosity test result of produced bio- grease samples with the standard mineral EP3 grease. The result indicated that sample 1, 2, and 10 exhibited lower viscosity. These types of greases cannot be used for high load or high temperature lubrication application.

Fig.15: Comparison of bio-grease samples with mineral EP3 on viscosity

Bio-grease sample 2, 4, 7, and 9 achieved moderate viscosity. In contrast sample 5, 6, and 8 demonstrated higher viscosity result compared to the other samples. Specifically sample 8 exhibited comparable viscosities with standard EP3 grease. Higher viscosity greases create a thicker film between moving surfaces, which can

better withstand heavy loads and prevent metal-to-metal contact, better sealing against contaminants, protecting the lubricated components.

5. Conclusion

An environmentally friendly bio-grease formulated using a blended of castor and jatropha oils as the base oil, lithium hydroxide as a thickener, and ZDDP as an additive. The characteristics and tribological performance of bio-grease were assessed by evaluating penetration, dropping point, wear, and coefficient of friction by using ASTM standards.

From the results, the following conclusions were derived.

- ✚ Effective film formation results in better lubrication by preventing contact between surfaces. The castor and jatropha oil ratio had a significant effect on minimization of wear and coefficient of friction (COF), with a higher amount of castor oil yielding favourable result. Using a higher amount of thickener and additive with minimum amount of jatropha oil, while keeping castor oil at its maximum level resulted in minimal wear scar diameter (WSD) and a lower COF. Sample 8 achieved the best performance in terms of wear (0.38 mm) and COF (0.035). Sample 5 also demonstrated excellent performance with wear value of 0.44mm and COF value of 0.04. Both samples achieved better result compared to mineral EP3 grease which exhibited a wear value of 0.47 and COF value of 0.045.
- ✚ Optimized values were obtained using statgraphics software for each response variable. As per the goal, the software determined a set of optimal values within the specified ranges of independent variables: a maximum dropping point temperature of 145.688°C, a maximum viscosity of 14.589 pa.s, a low wear value of 0.377 mm, a low coefficient of friction (COF) of 0.0265, and a cone penetration of 222.188 dmm, which corresponds to an NLGI grade 3 classification.
- ✚ In general, some formulated bio-grease samples demonstrated good result in almost all tests. These findings suggest that vegetable oil blends offer a viable alternative to mineral oil for bio-grease formulation.

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